

IMPORTANCE OF LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN THE WORKING ACTIVITY

Gulnora Ashrafovna Siyaeva

Associate professor of the Department of "Humanities and Foreign Languages" of the Fiscal Institute under the State Tax Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan PhD, Teaching subject is English

mob: +998911650626

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7084328>

Today, it is very important for everyone to know foreign languages. The world is becoming more and more globalized and knowing two languages is not just a fad, but a need of the hour. Learning foreign languages is a life skill for learning how to truly communicate and connect with others. Why should we learn foreign languages? I will now write about the reasons why you should learn foreign languages.[1]

1. Learning foreign languages grows your brain. Studies have shown the cognitive benefits of learning another language, no matter how old you are. These studies have shown that bilingual people have larger brains, better memory, creativity, problem solving, and more. These advantages make it easier not only to learn more languages, but to learn everything. The ability to switch tasks quickly is especially important in today's busy multitasking world. Bilinguals can switch tasks much more quickly than their monolingual counterparts and perform many other tasks at the same time.
2. Traveling becomes cheaper and easier when you learn a foreign language. Of course, many people are conscious of traveling. Knowing the language will be of great benefit to you when you travel to a foreign country. You can easily explain the food you want when you go out to eat. You can easily ask for directions from local people around you. If you take a guide with you, it will be more expensive.
3. Learning a foreign language opens the world to finding a job. It's no secret that learning a foreign language can improve your employment prospects. More companies than ever are doing business in several, often dozens of countries around the world, but they cannot do so without hiring people who understand at least one foreign language. Even at small local companies, the ability to speak a second language is likely to set you apart from other potential employers.
4. Makes new friends while learning a foreign language. Meeting new and interesting people and developing lifelong friendships are certainly goals worth pursuing, and learning another language is a surefire way to speed up the process. Language helps us to express our feelings, desires and connect with other people around us and forms meaningful relationships.

5. Learning a foreign language makes you more open-minded. Learning a foreign language and immersing yourself in a completely new culture and worldview is the surest way to become an open-minded, understanding, tolerant person, and it is absolutely priceless. Seeing the world from a different perspective and understanding where you and others are coming from is a fantastic, eye-opening experience.[5]

6. Learning foreign languages helps to better understand one's own language and culture. Learning a foreign language actually engages you in reverse psychology and allows you to better understand your native language and culture. This is one of the most unexpected benefits of learning a foreign language. You will become more aware not only of cultural customs, but also of the grammar, vocabulary and pronunciation patterns of your first language. This probably explains the improved listening, reading and writing skills that a foreign language provides to former monolinguals. The benefits of learning foreign languages have the ability to set you up for success in almost every aspect of your life. Learning a foreign language is very important and there are countless such reasons for learning a foreign language. Learning a foreign language helps overcome language barriers and connects people on a deeper level of mutual understanding. So, let's talk about why it is important for teachers who are not language experts to know the language. Especially nowadays teachers are required to know English. Why is this necessary? I would like to share my thoughts on this.[2] As everyone knows, English is recognized as the world language. One of the two young people is currently in the process of learning English. At least there is interest in this language. In order to educate such young people, I believe that any teacher in any field should have a basic knowledge of English. Because young people always love to imitate.[4] Also, knowledge of the English language is an excellent opportunity to develop the knowledge of teachers. The secret is that most scientific works are written in English. They will be able to read the original works easily. Another important aspect is that knowing English makes it easier to use today's modern technologies and social networks. English is also called the language of technology. [3] Almost all social networks are easily covered in English. Especially during the well-known pandemic, distance learning has started. This caused difficulties for many teachers. Because not all teachers know how to use modern techniques and social networks. Knowing English puts an end to these problems.

References:

1. Galskova N.D. Mejkulturnoe obuchenie problema yeley i sodrujanie obuchenie inostrannym yazykam. Inostranny yazyk v shkole 2004 - No. 1[1]
2. Jalolov J. J. Theory and practice of intercultural communication in the context of teaching intercultural communication through a foreign language or communicative-cumulative methodology. Proceedings of the republican scientific and practical conference. T- TDPU. 2008[2]
3. S. Saydaliev, Essays on foreign language teaching methodology, Namangan, 2004[3]
4. www.ziyonet.uz[4]
5. www.library.uz[5]

